

Photovoltaic properties of 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles and their derivatives

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Abstract : Photovoltaic property of 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles and their derivatives, 1-alkyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles have been studied. Light-energy conversion efficiency (η) is dependent on charge anisotropy in the molecule. Substitution of methyl group (1-Me) at imidazolyl ring increases the photovoltaic power conversion efficiency (η), fluorescence quantum yield (ϕ) and excited state life time (τ). DFT calculation has been carried out from the optimized structures and data are used to interpret the photovoltaic property of the compounds.

Keywords : 2-(Coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles, photovoltaic property, DFT computation.

Introduction

Dye sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) have been attracting substantial attention in recent years compared to the conventional p-n junction solid-state inorganic solar cells¹. Till date ruthenium polypyridyl complexes such as *cis*-dithiocyanato-bis(4,4'-dicarboxy-2,2'-bipyridine)-ruthenium(II), tri(thiocyanato)-4,4',4''-tricarboxy-2,2' : 6',2''-terpyridine ruthenium(II) (black dye) have been used in DSSCs as efficient photosensitizers²⁻⁶. Aromatic azo compounds have been of considerable interest in dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) and coumarinyl functionalized dyes in this regard produces interesting results⁷⁻¹¹. Use of coumarinyl functionalized molecules in this work is promising due to their rich photophysical properties. This work is concerned to the study of photovoltaic properties of 2-(coumarinyl-azo)imidazoles and their derivatives. We have also attempted to correlate the electronic and photovoltaic properties of the compounds with theoretical result by DFT calculations in gas phase.

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Coumarin, methyl iodide and imidazole were available from Sisco Research Lab, Mumbai, India. 4-Phenyl imidazole and

4-methyl imidazole were Sigma-Aldrich reagents (St. Louis, Missouri, USA). PVA from S. D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Boisar (MW 125000); PEO from BDH, England (MW 600000), LiClO₄ and EC (99.5% pure) were purchased from Fluka. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and were used without further purification. Commercially available SRL silica gel (60-120 mesh) was used for column chromatography.

Preparation of compounds :

Six different coumarinyl-azo-imidazoles i.e. 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazole (HCZ-4-H), 1-methyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazole (MeCZ-4-H), 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-4-methyl-imidazole (HCZ-4-Me), 1-methyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-4-methyl-imidazole (MeCZ-4-Me), 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-4-phenyl-imidazole (HCZ-4-Ph) and 1-methyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)-4-phenyl-imidazole (MeCZ-4-Ph) (Scheme 1) were synthesized following the similar procedure as 1-alkyl-2-(arylazo)imidazole¹².

Nitration of coumarin and its subsequent reduction to 6-aminocoumarin has been carried out by using conc. HNO₃ and Fe powder/NH₄Cl respectively. Diazocoumarin was prepared by adding NaNO₂ solution into 1 N HCl solution of 6-aminocoumarin at 0-5 °C at ice cold condition. Yellow solution of coumarinyl-6-diazonium ion was

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Scheme 1. 2-(Coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles and their derivatives.

filtered and filtrate was used for coupling reaction with imidazole, 4-methyl imidazole and 4-phenyl imidazole to prepare HCZ-4-H, HCZ-4-Me and HCZ-4-Ph respectively following reported procedure¹². Methylation of subsequent coumarin azoimidazoles i.e. HCZ-4-H, HCZ-4-Me and HCZ-4-Ph with sodium hydride (50% paraffin) and methyl iodide in dry tetrahydrofuran solvent resulted corresponding methylated products viz. MeCZ-4-H, MeCZ-4-Me and MeCZ-4-Ph.

HCZ-4-H (1a) : Found : C, 60.03; H, 3.29; N, 23.31. Calcd. for $C_{12}H_8N_4O_2$: C, 60.00; H, 3.33; N, 23.33%; FT IR (KBr disc) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1737 (COO), 1530 (C=N), 1405 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6 ; Me_4Si) : 6.62 (1H, m), 6.59 (1H, m), 7.34 (1H, s), 7.50 (1H, s), 8.07 (1H, m), 8.22 (1H, s), 8.25 (1H, d, J 9.2 Hz), 13.06 (1H, bs); MS (FAB⁺), m/z 241 (M+H)⁺. **HCZ-4-Me (1b)** : Found : C, 61.40; H, 3.97; N, 22.09. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{10}N_4O_2$: C, 61.42; H, 3.94; N, 22.05%; FT IR (KBr disc) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1723 (COO), 1561 (C=N), 1420 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6 ; Me_4Si) : 2.51 (3H, d, J 9.6 Hz), 6.55 (1H, m), 6.58 (1H, m), 7.54 (1H, q), 7.98 (1H, m), 8.17 (1H, s), 8.22 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 12.88 (1H, bs); MS (FAB⁺), m/z 255 (M+H)⁺. **HCZ-4-Ph (1c)** : Found : C, 68.4; H, 3.8; N, 17.8. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{12}N_4O_2$: C, 68.35; H, 3.8; N, 17.7%; FT IR (KBr disc) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1721 (COO), 1561 (C=N), 1431 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6 ; Me_4Si) : 6.60 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz), 6.62 (1H, d, J 6.9 Hz), 7.29–7.61 (5H, m), 7.91 (1H, s), 7.98 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz), 8.25 (1H, s), 8.27 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz), 13.27 (1H, bs); MS (FAB⁺), m/z 317

(M+H)⁺. **MeCZ-4-H (2a)** : Found : C, 61.45; H, 3.96; N, 22.07. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{10}N_4O_2$: C, 61.42; H, 3.94; N, 22.05%; FT IR (KBr disc) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1724 (COO), 1563 (C=N), 1431 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6 ; Me_4Si) : 6.50 (1H, m), 6.53 (1H, m), 7.21 (1H, s), 7.33 (1H, s), 7.84 (1H, m), 8.17 (1H, s), 8.20 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 4.09 (1H, s); MS (FAB⁺), m/z 255 (M+H)⁺. **MeCZ-4-Me (2b)** : Found : C, 62.71; H, 4.51; N, 20.94. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{12}N_4O_2$: C, 62.69; H, 4.48; N, 20.90%; FT IR (KBr disc) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1722 (COO), 1560 (C=N), 1443 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6 ; Me_4Si) : 2.35 (1H, d, J 9.6 Hz), 6.47 (1H, m), 6.51 (1H, m), 7.43 (1H, q), 7.82 (1H, m), 8.06 (1H, s), 8.13 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz), 3.95 (1H, s); MS (FAB⁺), m/z 269 (M+H)⁺. **MeCZ-4-Ph (2c)** : Found : C, 69.05; H, 4.28; N, 16.95. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{14}N_4O_2$: C, 69.1; H, 4.2; N, 17.0%; FT IR (KBr disc) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1722 (COO), 1565 (C=N), 1442 (N=N); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6 ; Me_4Si) : 4.16 (3H, s, Me), 6.26–7.61 (5H, m), 6.45 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz), 6.51 (1H, d, J 6.9 Hz), 7.35–7.61 (5H, m, Ph), 7.74 (1H, s), 7.90 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 8.18 (1H, s), 8.64 (1H, d, J 7.80 Hz); MS (FAB⁺), m/z 331 (M+H)⁺.

Sample preparation for photovoltaic measurements :

A thin film of the dye (coumarin azo compound) is prepared as mentioned in literature^{13,14}. The 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles have the absorption peak at 363–382 nm region. In a cleaned test tube, 1 g of PVA was mixed with 10 ml of double distilled water, warmed gently and stirred to make a transparent viscous solution of PVA. Also, 6 mg of coumarin azo is mixed with this solution. A solid electrolyte was prepared in a separate cleaned beaker by mixing PEO, LiClO_4 -EC and PC. The complex of PEO- LiClO_4 -EC-PC (30.60%–3.60%–19.60%–46.20% by weight) were mixed, stirred and heated around a temperature 60 °C for 4 h. This gel-like solid electrolyte is mixed with the previously made coumarin azo-PVA solution to form the blend. This blend is heated at 60 °C and stirred properly to mix them well for about 2 h. This viscous gel-like solution is then sandwiched between two electrodes. The electrodes were cleaned in chloroform solution and dried under vacuum about 2 h before use. The two electrical leads are taken out from the two ends of the electrodes. The complete

cell is dried in vacuum for about 6 h at around 60 °C before the final measurement. The active area of the cell was 0.04 cm². The structure of the cell is shown in Fig. 1. The above procedure is adopted for all the azo compounds.

Fig. 1. Structure of the electrochemical cell.

Photovoltaic measurements :

To measure the dark I-V characteristics, the cell is biased with a dc source with a series resistance of 56 K Ω . The current flowing through the device was estimated by measuring the voltage drop (measured by Agilent data acquisition unit, model no. 34970A) across this sensing resistance. For optical measurement, a tungsten lamp of 200 W is used. Incident light is allowed on the cell. By varying the intensity of incident radiation, voltage drops and hence the photocurrent across the sensing resistance is measured. The intensity is measured by a calibrated lux meter (Kyoritsu Electrical Instruments Works Ltd., Tokyo, model 5200). Photocurrent is measured by varying the intensity of light. To estimate the power curve the current is drawn from the cell for a constant illumination and a representative diagram is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Photo I-V characteristics of HCZ-4-H (1a) and MeCZ-4-H (2a).

From these curve the power conversion efficiency, short circuit current and fill factor is calculated. The power conversion efficiency of each cell can be estimated by using eq. (1),

$$\eta\% = [(I_{sc} \times V_{oc} \times FF)/\Phi_0] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

I_{sc} = short circuit current, V_{oc} = open circuit voltage, Φ_0 = the incident intensity of light and FF is defined by eq. (2),

$$FF = (V_m \times I_m)/(I_{sc} \times V_{oc}) \quad (2)$$

where V_m and I_m represent the voltage and current density at maximum power point, respectively. The estimated values of FF and power conversion efficiency are recorded at 1 Sun radiation.

Computational details :

All computations were performed using the Gaussian03 (G03) software¹⁵ *in vacuo*. Geometry optimization of 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles in the ground state have been performed with the Becke's three-parameter hybrid exchange functional and the Lee-Yang-Parr nonlocal correlation function (B3LYP)¹⁶. 6-31G basis set was used for the geometry optimization and the 6-31+G(d) basis set was used for time-dependent DFT study. The excitation energies and oscillator strength were calculated by the TD-DFT approach¹⁷. GaussSum was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital. This is done using Mulliken population analysis.

Results and discussion

The absorption spectra of 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles (HCZ-4-H (1a), HCZ-4-Me (1b), HCZ-4-Ph (1c)) exhibit two/three bands at 260–415 nm with high molar extinction coefficient value (ϵ , 10^3 – 10^4 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹). The band at 373–407 nm on N(1)-methylation, 1-methyl-2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles (MeCZ-4-H (2a), MeCZ-4-Me (2b), MeCZ-4-Ph (2c)) shifts the band maxima to longer wavelength by 7–16 nm (388–414 nm). From the analogy with the absorption spectrum of 1-alkyl-(2-arylazo)imidazole¹² it is proposed that the absorption band at \sim 370 nm corresponds to π - π^* transition, while tail $>$ 400 nm is due to n- π^* transition.

All the compounds show fluorescence spectra (Fig. 3) at 419–447 nm wavelengths when excited at 363–382 nm (Table 1). The fluorescence quantum yield has been determined with anthracene (ϕ , 0.62) and the value varies in 0.0012–0.0185 region. The methylated products show higher quantum yield value (0.0112–0.0185). Lifetime data of the compounds are taken in DMSO solvent on excitation at 370 nm. The decay profiles fit with biexponential curve (Fig. 4) and the average lifetime value in between 0.69 to 1.31 ns. The methylated compounds (MeCZ-4-H, MeCZ-4-Me, MeCZ-4-Ph) show higher lifetime value ($\tau > 1$ ns).

Photovoltaic property of the compounds is examined

Fig. 3. Electronic spectrum (—) and fluorescence spectrum (---) of HCZ-4-Me (**1b**) in DMSO.

Fig. 4. Decay profiles of (I) HCZ-4-Ph (**1c**) and (II) MeCZ-4-Me (**2b**) in DMSO. The excitation wavelength is 370 nm.

by self-designed system^{14,15}. The basic principle of ‘Solar cells’ in the conversion of sunlight to electricity has been shown by I-V characteristics (Fig. 5). Dye and conducting polymer blended material is placed between ITO glass anode and aluminium cathode. Photo-excitation of the dye results in the injection of an electron into the conduction band of the oxide film. The dye is regenerated by electron accepting from the electrolyte. The voltage generated under illumination corresponds to the difference between the Fermi level of the electron in the solid and the electrolyte. Thus device generates electric power from light without suffering any permanent chemical transformation. To compare the results of photo-current effect a dark phase of I-V curve of the compounds is shown in Fig. 5. There may be a physical change upon light irradiation (photochromism)¹². The growth of photocurrent and decay of a representative compound is shown in Fig. 6. The device competency is quantitatively as-

Table 1. UV-Vis^a, fluorescence^b and lifetime data^c

Compd.	UV-Vis data λ_{\max} (nm) ^a ($10^{-3} \epsilon/M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	λ_{ex} (nm) ^b	λ_{em} (nm) ^b	Quantum yield (ϕ) ^b	τ (ns) ^c	k_r ^c	k_{nr} ^c	χ^2
HCZ-4-H (1a)*	373 (13.47), 273 (6.92),	373	442	0.0012	0.797	0.00020	1.2542	1.17
HCZ-4-Me (1b)*	374 (18.57), 273 (17.62), 263 (20.19)	374	428	0.0021	0.685	0.00307	1.4574	1.18
HCZ-4-Ph (1c)*	407 (21.15), 370(s), 266 (22.59), 259 (23.25)	370	443	0.0024	0.891	0.00274	1.1193	1.19
MeCZ-4-H (2a)	388 (5.742), 371 (6.355), 276 (4.015)	371	419	0.0112	1.306	0.00858	0.7571	1.093
MeCZ-4-Me (2b)	400 (3.993), 363 (5.897), 277 (5.148)	363	447	0.0170	1.173	0.01450	0.8380	1.122
MeCZ-4-Ph (2c)	414(s) (5.280), 382 (6.264), 266 (9.488)	382	433	0.0185	1.223	0.00227	0.8154	1.100

^aSolvent, DMSO at 298 K.

^bSolvent, DMSO at 298 K.

^cExcitation at 370 nm in benzene solution at 298 K, k_r and k_{nr} are radiative and non-radiative rate constants.

^dFluorescence and lifetime data are not recorded for these compounds.

*Reference [18].

Fig. 5. The dark I-V curve of HCZ-4-Ph (1c) and MeCZ-4-Ph (2c).

Fig. 6. Photocurrent growth of MeCZ-4-Me : Intensity (a) 6.46 mW/cm², (b) 12.92 mW/cm², (c) 19.36 mW/cm², (d) 25.84 mW/cm², (e) 32.30 mW/cm², (f) 38.76 mW/cm², (g) 45.22 mW/cm², (h) 51.68 mW/cm², (j) 58.14 mW/cm², (k) 64.6 mW/cm².

signed by incident photon to current conversion efficiency (η), corresponds to the number of electrons measured as photocurrent in the external circuit divided by the monochromatic photon flux that strikes the cell and in general it is found that the compounds **2** exhibits better power

Table 2. Photovoltaic parameters of the compounds (**1**, **2**)

Dye	V_{oc} (mV)	I_{sc} (nA)	Intensity (mW/cm ²)	η (%)	FF
HCZ-4-H (1a)	32.3	11.2	64.6	0.00065	0.74
HCZ-4-Me (1b)	3.89	42.6	100	0.0022	0.741
HCZ-4-Ph (1c)	0.143	144.4	64.6	0.000047	0.84
MeCZ-4-H (2a)	42.64	86.81	32.3	0.0166	0.816
MeCZ-4-Me (2b)	75.3	66.3	51.68	0.018	0.92
MeCZ-4-Ph (2c)	21.72	56.2	32.3	0.0033	0.496

conversion efficiency than **1** (Table 2). The electron donating ability of -Me substituent at N(1)-imidazolyl group may influence the photocurrent activity.

The DFT calculation shows that 2-(coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles are electronically anisotropic (Fig. 7). There are two charge-separated centers in a molecule to perform photoconductivity. The HOMO is the source of conducting charge and is controlled by imidazolyl group (donor moiety) while charge is accepted by LUMO. Azocoumarinyl group is charge deficient (acceptor) (LUMO contains ~48% azo function and ~29% coumarinyl function), while imidazolyl group is donor centre (HOMO contains 50–80% imidazolyl group) (Fig. 8). Substitution in imidazole has specific effect to monitor energy of HOMO and charge density. N-Methyl group in compounds **2** influence HOMO due to the +I effect of methyl group and increases power conversion efficiency. The power conversion efficiency (η) follows a trend **2c** < **2b** < **2a** which may be supported from increase in electron density in imidazolyl motif. The effect of N-alkyl substituent on photovoltaic efficiency is under detail study.

Fig. 7. Mulliken atomic charges of HCZ-4-Ph. Hydrogens are omitted for clarity.

Fig. 8. Surface plots of the frontier orbitals (HOMO and LUMO) of HCZ-4-Ph (**1c**) and MeCZ-4-Ph (**2c**) alongwith percentage of contribution of constituting function.

Conclusion

2-(Coumarinyl-6-azo)imidazoles and their derivatives exhibit photovoltaic effect. The photovoltaic power conversion efficiency, although not profitable at this stage, has shown a promise towards the design of light-energy conversion devices. However power conversion increment is observed on methylation to imidazolyl group. DFT computation reveals that the molecule is electronically anisotropic : imidazole is electron donor and azo-coumarinyl group is electron acceptor and may be the reason for photoconductivity.

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